

Molecular docking, microwave-assisted synthesis, characterization, and preliminary evaluation of the anti-microbial activity of new sulfonamide derivatives of the 1, 2, 4-triazole-3-thiol ring system

Ali Abdulhadi Mosleh¹, Zainab A. Dakhel²

¹ Ministry of Health and Environments, Al Rusafa Health Directorate, Baghdad, Iraq

² Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq

Corresponding author: Ali Abdulhadi Mosleh (ali.abd2100m@copharm.uobaghdad.edu.iq)

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Abstract

A new sulfonamide derivative containing a 1,2,4-Triazole-3-thiol ring was synthesized and characterized using FT-IR and ¹H-NMR. The microwave-assisted chemical synthesis of the 1,2,4-Triazole-3-thiol ring system resulted in good yield and purity. The synthetic compounds were then subjected to in vitro evaluation for antimicrobial study. All synthetic compounds show high activity against Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*, *S. pneumoniae*, and *B. subtilis*) and high activity against Gram-negative bacteria (*P. aeruginosa*, and *H. pylori*), with less activity against (*N. gonorrhoea*, and *E. coli*). Also, it shows high activity against fungi (*C. albicans*). In this study, we utilized computational methods to design new derivatives that target the carbonic anhydrase enzyme of *H. pylori* (PDB: 4YGF). All the target compounds interact with the enzyme's active site, resulting in a disturbance of the acid-base balance affecting the virulence and pathogenicity.

Keywords

Sulfonamide derivatives, 1,2,4-Triazole-4-thiol, Microwave, *H. pylori*, Carbonic anhydrase

Introduction

The main cause of drug resistance in the healthcare setting is the excessive and incorrect consumption of different antimicrobial agents. Infections caused by resistant bacteria are treated by administering different antibiotics to which they may still be sensitive. However, bacteria may acquire resistance to these new classes of antibiotics, becoming multi-resistant organisms. Therefore, it is crucial to discover

new types of antibiotics that can overcome the resistance in these microorganisms (Campestre et al. 2021). Many strategies have been taken to find novel antibacterial compounds capable of fighting resistant organisms (Alani et al. 2024). Sulfonamides are an important class in the area of medicinal chemistry due to their wide variety of pharmacological activities, including antimicrobial (Lihumis et al. 2023), anti-inflammatory (Jiao et al. 2024), anti-cancer (Elsayad et al. 2024), anti-glaucoma (Angeli et al. 2024), and anti-diabetic

properties (Naim et al. 2018). Sulfonamides work as antimicrobial agents through two main mechanisms. The primary mechanism involves targeting and inhibiting the bacterial dihydropteroate synthase (DHPS). This inhibition leads to a defect in the synthesis of tetrahydrofolic acid (THF), disrupting the supply of thymidine, which results in the arrest of DNA biosynthesis and ultimately affects bacterial growth (Zessel et al. 2014). Several DHPS mutations are responsible for the sulfonamide resistance; there is another mechanism involved in the inhibition of bacterial carbonic anhydrase by targeting the zinc-binding domain that leads to disturbances in the acid/base balance, which reduces the pathogenicity and virulence of various bacteria, including *H. pylori*, *V. cholera*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. enterica* (Supuran and Capasso 2020). The chemical synthesis of the heterocyclic ring is an integral part of medicinal chemistry, with different pharmacological activities including anti-inflammatory (Paprocka et al. 2023), antiviral (Farghaly et al. 2024), anti-cancer (Abbas et al. 2023), and antimicrobial (Karnaš et al. 2024). The triazole ring system can target various mammalian and pathogenic proteins by creating a network of bonds at the proteins' active sites, easily forming various weak interactions, such as H-bonds, dipole-dipole interactions, and π -stacking (Rahman et al. 2023). This capability to inhibit various proteins makes the triazole ring system an intriguing option for the chemical design of new therapeutic agents. The incorporation of a triazole ring into various drug candidates has been of interest in recent years for designing new classes or improving existing ones. Among them, the sulfonamide-containing triazole ring system is noteworthy (Naaz et al. 2018).

Materials and methods

Molecular docking

The first step was to access the Protein Data Bank and retrieve the *Helicobacter pylori* crystal structure (PDB: 4YGF). We eliminated water molecules over 5 Å from the binding site to focus on the ligand interaction region. To mimic the conditions in the body, the current study prepared the proteins at a pH of 7. This procedure involved optimizing hydrogen atoms and assigning bond ordering. Following this, the current study optimized the protein structure using the OPLS4 force field, a well-known force field for biomolecular simulations in molecular mechanics. Additionally, the ligand was prepared at a pH of 7 ± 2 using the OPLS4 force field. This was done to ensure that the ligand molecule's shape and net charge matched physiological conditions. The current study also considered the addition of the metal binding state of the ligands. We used a grid-based approach to accurately identify the precise region of interest for the docking simulations, where the binding site is located. This process involved creating a grid with the co-crystallized ligand, which provided crucial information about the appropriate binding pocket for the new ligand. We placed the native ligand at the center

of the grid and constructed a rectangular solid with measurements of 20 Å around it. For the docking simulation, we used Glide, an advanced docking software program developed by Schrödinger (version 2023). We used typical precision docking with flexible sampling of the ligand to thoroughly investigate the interactions between the ligand and protein inside the specific binding pocket. By employing this method, we evaluated candidate binding positions and anticipated the binding configurations that would yield the highest energy stability between the ligand and the protein target (Lu et al. 2021; Yang et al. 2021).

Materials

Chemicals and solvents used in the synthesis were obtained from various companies without further purification before use. The Stuart SMP30 was utilized to measure the melting point of intermediate and final compounds. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was utilized to confirm the reactions' progress and assess the compounds' purity by employing different mobile phases. The FT-IR spectrophotometer is manufactured by the Japanese company Shimadzu. A Bruker model Ultra Shield (300, and 400 MHz) spectrophotometer was utilized to acquire $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra, with DMSO- d_6 serving as the solvent.

General procedure

The process for producing intermediate and final compounds is described in Scheme 1. The reaction of acetanilide with chlorosulfonic acid produces N-acetylsulfonylchloride as an intermediate (1). The fusion of different carboxylic acids with thiocarbonylhydrazide results in the formation of a 1, 2, 4-Triazole-3-thiol ring (2a–c) with good yield and purity. The combination of intermediate (1) with a 1, 2, 4-Triazole-3-thiol ring in the presence of pyridine as a catalyst creates compounds (3a–c).

Synthesis of 4-acetamidobenzenesulfonylchloride, compound (1)

In a dry conical flask containing (2.7 g, 20 mmol) of acetanilide, immerse the flask in an ice bath. Chloro-sulfonic acid (8 ml, 120 mmol) was added from the dropping funnel all at once and immediately connected to the conical flask, which contained some amount of water to trap the liberated gas. The solution is rapidly stirred, keeping the temperature below 20 °C. The flask was heated in a water bath at 70–80 °C for 20 min, to complete the reaction after the acetanilide had mostly dissolved and the initial exothermic reaction had subsided. Once the flask had cooled to room temperature, it was transferred into a 250 ml beaker holding 100 g of crushed ice, and stirred by glass rod to prevent the formation of large lumps. The precipitate was collected by vacuum filtration and washed with cold distilled water till the filtrate was neutral to PH paper (Ovung and Bhat-tacharyya 2021). After the product was dried, washed with toluene, and recrystallized from chloroform to give a white to cream-beige solid, yield 75%, melting point 143–145 °C.

Scheme 1. General synthetic pathway of target compounds.

Synthesis of 1, 2, 4-Triazole-3-thiol, compound (2a–c)

A mixture consisting of (10 mmol) of thiocarbohydrazide and (15 mmol) of the liquid carboxylic acids was microwave-irradiated for the appropriate duration of time at (145 °C). The reaction's progress was tracked using thin-layer chromatography (TLC). The reactions were typically completed within a time frame of 30 to 60 minutes. Following the completion of the reaction, chilled distilled water was added, and the solid that had been formed was separated by filtration and subsequently purified through recrystallization with ethanol (Safonov et al. 2021).

Synthesis of sulfonamide derivatives, compound (3a–c)

To the stirred ice-cold solution consisting of 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (1 mmol) in THF (8 ml) and pyridine (1.5 mmol). The 4-acetamidobenzene sulfonyl chloride (1 mmol) was added gradually. Then, the solution was left to be stirred at room temperature (25 °C), under argon gas for 24 h; the precipitate was formed, filtered out, and recrystallized from ethanol (Capurso et al. 2019).

Physical properties and spectral analysis

4-amino-4H-1, 2, 4-triazole-3-thiol, compound (2a)

White powder, yield 60%, m.p. 157–159 °C. FT-IR ($\nu = \text{cm}^{-1}$): 3275, 3159 (Asym. & sym. str. of NH₂); 3113 (aromatic, C-H str.), 2607 (S-H str.), 1604 (C=N str.), 1215 (C=S str.), 659 (C-S str.). ¹H-NMR: (300 MHz, DMSO-d = ppm): 5.70(s, 2H, NH₂-), 8.50(s, 1H, CH-), 13.60(s, 1H, SH).

4-amino-5-methyl-4H-1, 2, 4-triazole-3-thiol, compound (2b)

White crystals, yield 50%, m.p. 182–184 °C. FT-IR ($\nu = \text{cm}^{-1}$): 3267, 3170 (Asym. & sym. str. of NH₂), 3059,

2943 (Asym. & sym. str. of CH₃), 2746 (S-H str.), 1627 (C=N str.), 1215 (C=S str.), 659 (C-S str.). ¹H-NMR: (300 MHz, DMSO-d = ppm): 2.25(s, 3H, CH₃-), 5.50(s, 2H, NH₂-), 13.40(s, 1H, SH).

4-amino-5-ethyl-4H-1, 2, 4-triazole-3-thiol, compound (2c)

Light-brown crystals, yield 70%, m.p. 140–142 °C. FT-IR ($\nu = \text{cm}^{-1}$): 3267, 3224 (Asym. & sym. str. of NH₂), 2985, 2954 (Asym. & sym. str. of CH₃), 2935, 2885 (Asym. & sym. str. of CH₂), 2669 (S-H str.), 1612 (C=N str.), 1238 (C=S str.), 667 (C-S str.). ¹H-NMR: (400 MHz, DMSO-d = ppm): 1.20(t, 3H, CH₃-), 2.60(q, 2H, CH₂-), 5.55(s, 2H, NH₂-), 13.45(s, 1H, SH).

N-(4-(N-(3-mercapto-4H-1, 2, 4-triazol-4-yl)sulfamoyl)phenyl)acetamide, compound (3a)

White powder, yield 70%, m.p. 123–125 °C. FT-IR ($\nu = \text{cm}^{-1}$): 3379 (N-H str. of SO₂N-H), 3109 (aromatic, C-H str. overlap with C-H str. of triazole ring), 1693 (C=O str. amide I band); 1635 (N-H ben. of SO₂N-H), 1589 (N-H ben. amide II band) 1527, 1489 (aromatic, C=C str.) 1315, 1157 (Asym. & sym. str. of SO₂), 1261 (C-N str.). ¹H-NMR: (300 MHz, DMSO-d = ppm): 10.02(s, 1H, NH of triazole), 8.95(s, 1H, -NH-SO₂), 8.60(s, 1H, -NH-C=O), 8.50(s, 1H, CH of triazole), 8.09(d, 2H, Ar-SO₂), 7.53(d, 2H, Ar-N-), 2.06(s, 3H, CH₃-).

N-(4-(N-(3-mercapto-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-4-yl)sulfamoyl)phenyl)acetamide, compound (3b)

White powder, yield 50%, m.p. 122–124 °C. FT-IR ($\nu = \text{cm}^{-1}$): 3379 (N-H str. of SO₂NH), 3109 (aromatic, C-H str.), 2862, 2785 (Asym. & sym. str. of CH₃), 1693 (C=O str. amide I band), 1635 (N-H bend. of SO₂N-H), 1589 (N-H bend. amide II band), 1527, 1489 (aromatic, C=C str.), 1315, 1157 (Asym. & sym. str. of SO₂), 1257 (C-N str.). ¹H-NMR: (300 MHz, DMSO-d = ppm): 10.02(s, 1H, NH of triazole), 8.95(s, 1H, -NH-SO₂), 8.60(s, 1H, -NH-C=O),

8.05–8.10(d, 2H, Ar-SO₂), 7.52(d, 2H, Ar-N-), 2.06(s, 3H, CH₃-CO), 2.04(s, 3H, CH₃ of triazole).

***N*-(4-(*N*-(3-ethyl-5-mercapto-4*H*-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)sulfamoyl)phenyl)acetamide, compound (3c)**

White powder, yield 65%, m.p. 119–121 °C. FT-IR ($\nu = \text{cm}^{-1}$): 3379 (N-H str. of SO₂N-H), 3109 (aromatic, C-H str.), 2997, 2835 (Asym. & sym. str. of CH₃), 2962, 2775 (Asym. & sym. str. of CH₂), 1693 (C=O str. amide I band), 1635 (N-H bend. of SO₂N-H), 1589 (N-H bend. amide II band), 1527, 1489 (aromatic, C=C str.), 1315, 1157 (Asym. & sym. str. of SO₂), 1261 (C-N str.). ¹H-NMR: (300 MHz, DMSO-d = ppm): 9.98(s, 1H, NH of triazole), 8.88(s, 1H, -NH-SO₂), 8.55(s, 1H, -NH-C=O), 7.93–8.21 (d, 2H, Ar-SO₂), 7.40–7.48(d, 2H, Ar-N-), 2.47–2.41(q, 2H, CH₂ of ethyl group), 2.02(s, 3H, CH₃-CO) 1.95(t, 3H, CH₃ of ethyl group).

In vitro anti-microbial study

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), along with the agar diffusion method, was used to assess the antimicrobial activity of the target derivatives against several microorganisms, including Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*, *S. pneumoniae*, and *B. subtilis*), Gram-negative bacteria (*P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, *N. gonorrhoeae*, and *H. pylori*), and fungal species (*C. albicans*). Diluted solutions were created from a stock solution (10 mg/ml) of each derivative, at concentrations ranging from 10–1000 mcg/ml. The solutions were prepared on a microtiter plate. The diluent employed was Mueller-Hinton broth. Each well was inoculated with 20 μl of a bacterial suspension with an equivalent concentration to McFarland standard no. 0.5 (1.5 \times 10⁸CFU/ml), except for the negative control wells. After that, the microtiter plates were put in an incubation chamber and kept at a temperature of 37 °C for 18 to 20 hours. After the incubation period, a volume of 20 μl of resazurin dye was added to each well. The samples were incubated for 2 hours to observe any color changes. The sub-MIC concentrations in the resazurin broth assay have been determined by visually observing the lowest concentrations in the broth micro dilutions at which the color transformed from blue to pink. Sulfadiazine, sulfamethoxazole, and fluconazole served as standard antibiotics (Franconi and Lupetti 2023).

The well diffusion assay was carried out using a bacterial suspension of approximately 1.5 \times 10⁸ CFU/ml obtained from the McFarland turbidity standard (number 0.5). The procedure involved applying the substance to the surface of MHA plates using a swab and allowing the excess fluids to dry in a sterile hood. Four wells were created in each agar plate containing the microorganisms under examination, and 80 μL of the test chemical was added to each well. The plates were then placed in an incubator at 30 °C for 72 hours for fungal species and at 37 °C for 24 hours for bacterial species. The zone of inhibition (ZI) width around each well was measured in millimeters to assess the antimicrobial activity (Subramaniam et al. 2020).

Statistical analysis

All the experiments were performed and reported in triplicate. The average mean values were reported along with standard deviation values. The T-test was used to assess the data's significance and compare the mean ($\alpha < 0.05$). The software used for statistical analysis is (R Studio 4.5 and the figures by Origin Lab 2021 software).

Results and discussion

Chemistry

The synthesis of new sulfonamide derivatives (3a–c) was achieved through the straightforward substitution of an aryl sulfonyl chloride with 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol, as illustrated in Scheme 1. The fusion of liquid carboxylic acid with thiocarbohydrazide under microwave irradiation for an appropriate time and temperature yields compounds (2a–c). Microwave irradiation facilitates the nucleophilic attack of the amine group of thiocarbohydrazide on the carbonyl group of the carboxylic acid, forming a tetrahedral intermediate. The intramolecular cyclization proceeds through the formation of an intermediate known as (1-acylthiocarbohydrazide) (Kurzer and Wilkinson 1970), as shown in Scheme 2. The compounds (3a–c) are formed by stirring compounds (2a–c) with compound (1) in the presence of pyridine as a catalyst and THF as a solvent. The substitution reaction at RSO₂X is similar to the nucleophilic attack at RCOX. Although sulfonyl halides are less reactive than carboxylic acid halides, many reactions share fundamental similarities. The reaction proceeded through the S_N-2 type mechanism (Smith 2007; Dakhel and Mohammed 2017). Compounds (2a–c) are characterized by the presence of two bands around 3270–3150 cm⁻¹, representing the asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching vibration of primary amine, respectively. Also, the bands around 1615 cm⁻¹ for (C=N) stretching, and around 1200 cm⁻¹ for (C=S) stretching identified the synthesis of these compounds. A single band around 3370 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the vibrations of sulfonamide groups' (N-H) bonds, confirms the successful synthesis of the desirable compounds (3a–c). The successful chemical synthesis of the intermediate and target compounds was confirmed via ¹H-NMR analysis. All the synthesized compounds (2a–c), show a singlet peak of around 13.5 ppm for (SH), and a singlet peak of around 5.5 ppm for (NH₂). Compound (2c), shows two additional peaks, the quartet peak around 2.5 ppm for (CH₂) and the triplet peak around 1 ppm for (CH₃). Compound (2b), shows an additional peak of around 2 ppm for (CH₃) that directly binds to the triazole ring. Compound (2a), has characterized a peak of around 8.5 ppm for the (C-H) of triazole ring. There are clear singlet peaks in all of the spectra at 10 ppm for the (N-H) of the triazole ring, and around 9 ppm for (N-H) of sulfonamide groups. In addition, there is a singlet peak at around 8 ppm for the (N-H) of the amide bonds.

Scheme 2. Mechanism of synthesis of compound (2a–c).

Docking study

This section will focus on the binding interactions and affinities of various compounds with carbonic anhydrase, particularly the critical interactions within the enzyme's active site and their impact on binding efficiency. A relatively high binding affinity of acetazolamide is indicated by its docking score of -6.2 kcal/mol. Several significant interactions support this strong binding. These include hydrogen bonds between the amide group and Asn 108, the sulfonamide group and Thr 191, and the sulfonamide group and the zinc ion Zn301. The ligand is stabilized within the enzyme's active site as a result of these interactions, which also enhance the inhibitory effect of the enzyme. The highest docking score, -7.05 , as compared to acetazolamide was achieved for compound (3a). This high affinity arises from extensive interactions, including multiple bonds with Zn301 via the sulfur substituent of the triazole, two π - π stacking interactions with His 110 and His 84, and a hydrogen bond with Trp 23 through its amide group. These strong interactions make clear the superior binding efficiency of this compound. The poorer binding affinity of compound (3c), with a score of -1.2 , is evident from its limited interactions, including only a coordination bond between the triazole sulfur substituent and Zn301 and a hydrogen bond with Trp 23, with a lack of other major interactions contributing to its low binding score. A strong binding affinity with a score of -6.75 was displayed by the compound (3b). This compound formed extensive coordination bonds, a total of four, with Zn301 and hydrogen bonds between its sulfonamide group and Asn 108, its amide group, and Thr 191, as shown in Table 1.

Docking validation was conducted by redocking the reference ligand and comparing the redocked conformation with the original conformation of the co-crystallized (Wadi et al. 2023), as shown in Fig. 1.

The red molecule represents the reference ligand from the crystal structure, while the blue molecule represents the redocked ligand. The minimal differences in conformation between the red and blue ligands indicate a successful docking protocol validation. The RMS value is 3.5 Å.

Table 1. Docking score in (kcal/mol).

Compounds	Docking score
3a	-7.05
3b	-6.75
3c	-1.2
Acetazolamide	-6.2
Sulfamethoxazole	-3.83
Sulfadiazine	-2.5

Figure 1. The docking validation was performed by redocking the co-crystallized ligand.

The interaction of acetazolamide, and compounds (3a–c) with the target proteins (PBD: 4YGF) are shown in Fig. 2.

Anti-microbial study

The antibacterial activity of the targeted compounds was tested against various strains of bacteria as compared to the standard antibacterial drugs (Sulfamethoxazole and sulfadiazine). Additionally, the antifungal activity against (*C. albicans*) was evaluated as compared to the standard antifungal drug (fluconazole) as displayed in Table 2.

The MIC results of the target compounds can be presented in a column chart, as shown in Fig. 3.

The zone of inhibition was measured in millimeters using the agar diffusion method based on MIC results and is illustrated in Table 3.

Based on the data presented in (Table 3), the mean \pm SD for *S. aureus* is 29.8 ± 2.55 . The T-test indicates a strong correlation between the zone of Inhibition (3a–c, Sulfadiazine,

Figure 3. This figure illustrates the more potent compound with a small MIC value.

Sulfamethoxazole, Fluconazole, and DMSO) and *S. aureus*, with a p-value less than 0.001. Similarly, for *S. pneumoniae*, the mean \pm SD is 31.6 ± 2.07 . The T-test shows a strong correlation with the same set of inhibitors, with a p-value less than 0.00001. *B. subtilis* has a mean \pm SD of 23.4 ± 3.13 . The T-test indicates a strong correlation with the Zone of Inhibition (3a–c, Sulfadiazine, Sulfamethoxazole, Fluconazole, and DMSO), with a p-value less than 0.005. For *E. coli*, the mean \pm SD is 17 ± 6.29 , and the T-test also shows a strong correlation with the same inhibitors, with a p-value less than 0.01. *P. aeruginosa* exhibits a mean \pm SD of 25 ± 3.2 , and the T-test reveals a strong correlation with the zone of Inhibition (3a–c, Sulfadiazine, Sulfamethoxazole, Fluconazole, and DMSO), with a p-value less than 0.001. *N. gonorrhoeae* has a mean \pm SD of 11.5 ± 7.23 , with the T-test showing no correlation with the inhibitors, resulting in a p-value of 0.05. *H. pylori*, with a mean \pm SD of 33.2 ± 3.96 , shows a strong correlation with the zone of Inhibition (3a–c, Sulfadiazine, Sulfamethoxazole, Fluconazole, and DMSO), with a p-value less than 0.05. Lastly, *C. albicans*, with a mean \pm SD of 31.25 ± 2.36 , demonstrates a strong correlation with the same set of inhibitors, indicated by a p-value less than 0.05. The data indicate varying levels of susceptibility to the inhibitors across different microorganisms. *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae*: Both show strong correlations with the inhibitors, with very low p-values (<0.001 and <0.00001 , respectively), suggesting the high effectiveness of the inhibitors against these bacteria. The close mean values and low standard deviations indicate consistent results within each group. *B. subtilis*: Exhibits a strong correlation with the inhibitors, with a p-value less than 0.005, indicating that the inhibitors are quite effective. However, the slightly higher standard deviation compared to *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae* suggests more variability in response. *E. coli*: Shows a significant correlation with the inhibitors, but the p-value is slightly higher (<0.01), and the standard deviation is notably larger, indicating more variability in its susceptibility. *P. aeruginosa*: Also exhibits a strong correlation, with a p-value less than 0.001, suggesting high susceptibility to the inhibitors, though variability is still present as indicated by the standard deviation. *N. gonorrhoeae*: Displays the lowest mean Zone of Inhibition and the highest standard deviation, with a p-value of 0.05, suggesting no significant

correlation with the inhibitors. This indicates that *N. gonorrhoeae* is likely resistant to the inhibitors tested. *H. pylori* and *C. albicans* show strong correlations with the inhibitors, with p-values less than 0.05, indicating effectiveness. *H. pylori*, with the highest mean Zone of Inhibition, shows a relatively lower standard deviation, suggesting consistent susceptibility. *C. albicans* also shows consistent results but with a slightly higher variability than *H. pylori*. In summary, while the inhibitors are broadly effective against most tested microorganisms, *N. gonorrhoeae* appears to be an outlier with resistance to the inhibitors. These findings highlight the need for tailored antimicrobial strategies for different pathogens, particularly those demonstrating resistance. The boxplot of the zone of the inhibition is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. The boxplot of the zone of inhibition (3a–c, Sulfadiazine, Sulfamethoxazole, Fluconazole, and DMSO) and the isolations.

Conclusion

The synthesis of a new series of sulfonamide derivatives was accomplished with successful results. Their chemical structures were determined using FT-IR spectroscopy and $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy. The presence of a new band around 3370 cm^{-1} in FT-IR, and a singlet peak around 9 ppm in $^1\text{H-NMR}$ indicate the synthesis of target compounds. Compounds (3b, and 3c) can target the zinc-binding domain of the carbonic anhydrase enzyme of *H. pylori* (PDB: 4YGF) via the sulfur atom in the triazole ring system. In

contrast, compound (3a) interacts via sulfur atom, and the sulfonamide group reflected the higher binding affinity. All final compounds exhibit significant efficacy against Gram-positive bacteria, including (*S. aureus*, *S. pneumoniae*, and *B. subtilis*). Most of the synthesized compounds show high activity against G-negative bacteria, including (*P. aeruginosa*, and *H. pylori*), with lower activity against (*N. gonorrhoeae* and *E. coli*). All the synthesized target compounds exhibit a high activity against *C. albicans*. The MIC results show that compound (3a) can inhibit a variety of bacterial strains at low concentrations when compared to another synthetic compound. According to both the MIC and zone on inhibitions results compound (3a) has slightly more potent activity against *C. albicans* than the standard antifungal drug fluconazole.

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Author contribution

Ali, as the first author, contributed to the synthesis of the final compounds, analyzed the FT-IR and ¹H-NMR data, and assessed the antibacterial activity. Zainab, the second author, approved the final version after reviewing the results.

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